

A Quantum Free Particle Does Not Seem to Maximize Spatial Entropy Part II

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In Part I, we noted that the classical mechanical probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$ for a constant p, v in a length L maximized entropy in this length as all x points have the same probability. It seems, however, from experiment that one cannot have infinite x resolution. In many cases, classical particle positions are measured by bouncing photons which have a wavelength. Even if this wavelength becomes smaller and smaller with increasing energy, it is still finite. Thus, we suggest that there does not exist any experimental evidence for infinite x resolution and that one must consider a ruler with gradations.

In Part I, we argued that these gradations in space suggest that spatial entropy is not maximized. Here we note that although these gradations give order to space, the distance between two gradation marks is not measurable by a particle with momentum p . In such a case, each of these x points should have equal probability weight, or entropy between gradations should be maximized. This may be accomplished by using the periodic function $\exp(ibx)$ because each dx is used in the argument $b dx$ represents the same $d\theta$ angle, hence one is maximizing entropy within a circle with one rotation still denoting a length of x/b . We also note that if $\exp(ibx)$ is considered to be a probability and b is considered to be a dynamic variable, then candidates are kinetic energy, momentum and velocity. $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x) = \exp(i(b_1+b_2)x)$ suggests a quantity that is always conserved and this suggests that $b=p$.

Thus, we suggest that even though the spatial gradations give order to space and break maximum entropy suggested by $P(x)dx = dx/L$ which assumes infinite x resolution which does not seem to exist, there is still maximum entropy in the x points between gradations.

Classical Mechanical Probability and Infinite X Resolution

Newtonian mechanics seems to assume infinite spatial resolution and so one has the maximum spatial entropy within a length L of:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

Experimentally, however, one must measure the center of mass of a classical particle which is done usually with light. A photon, however, has a wavelength and even if this becomes small, it does not become zero. Furthermore, different energy photons have different wavelengths suggesting that one does not have a fixed ruler gradation system.

As a result, one cannot have ((1)) hold. Rather, it seems that one must have gradations in space which give order to space. The point we wish to make in this note is that between gradation marks, one has no preference for one x or another. (These are interpolated x points for a given gradation.) Thus, one may assume maximum spatial entropy within gradation marks.

The question then becomes: How does one mathematically describe a system with gradations with x points between the gradations having equal weight or maximum entropy? We suggest that the function:

$$\exp(ibx) \quad ((2))$$

which is written in polar co-ordinates with a radius of 1 satisfies this requirement. Here b is unknown, but we suggest that it should be linked with some kind of dynamic variable because if one tries to set the gradation marks in space in an orderly fashion, one either starts at the left or right and moves along smoothly.

The argument bx means that each $b \, dx$ has the same weight in the periodic function, i.e. all x points within gradations have equal probability and there is maximum entropy between gradations. At the same, one revolution, i.e. bx changing from 0 to 2π yields two gradation marks. Thus, the gradation structure as well as equal probability within gradations is present.

Link with $P(x)dx = dx/L$

As a result, $\exp(ibx)$ contains both gradation marks and maximum entropy between these marks. If one were to remove the periodic gradations with $1/b$ spacings, one would simply have maximum entropy everywhere. This may be done by writing $\exp(-ibx)\exp(ibx)$. This then creates a link with $P(x)dx=dx/L$.

Link With Conservation of Momentum

Given the suggesting that b in $\exp(ibx)$ should be a dynamical variable, we note that if $\exp(ibx)$ represents a kind of probability, then:

$$\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x) = \exp(i(b_1+b_2)x) \quad ((3))$$

Possible dynamical variables are v (velocity), kinetic energy and momentum, but only the latter is guaranteed to be always conserved. Thus, we suggest $b=p$.

p and $-p$ and Parity

Even though we suggest the probability $\exp(ipx)$, this may be written as a sum of a symmetric p and $-p$ term plus an antisymmetric one, i.e.

$$\exp(ipx) = \{ \exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \} + \{ \exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx) \} \quad ((4))$$

Also

$$\exp(-ipx) = \{ \exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) \} + \{ \exp(-ipx) - \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((5))$$

The first term in $\{ \}$ does not change if one changes p to $-p$ and so one has positive parity, but the second term changes sign. Furthermore, we note that $\exp(ipx)$ may be written in terms of sums of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, i.e. clockwise and counter-clockwise rotations. At first this may not

seem like being particularly relevant, but we note that the symmetric term is proportional to $\cos(px)$ and the antisymmetric one to $i \sin(px)$, i.e. the two dimensional components.

Thus, one starts with two dimensional polar co-ordinates with $r=1$ and θ being changed in two directions and by using clockwise and counter-clockwise rotations, one creates the two-dimensional space $(\cos(px), \sin(px))$ and the idea of parity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we noted in Part I, that $P(x)dx=dx/L$ maximizes entropy by treating each x point as having the same weight. Experimentally, however, we argue that one cannot have infinite x resolution because photons used to measure have wavelengths. Thus, there is always a set of ruler gradations which give order and so maximum entropy, even over length L , does not exist.

In this note, we suggest that even though gradations exist and create order, one may consider maximum entropy for x points between two gradation lines. This suggests the form $\exp(ibx)$ where b is some kind of dynamical variable because one creates the gradations by moving from the left to right or vice versa. One may see that as bx moves from 0 to 2π one creates two gradation marks. In between, however, $b dx$ all have the same value, i.e. $d\theta$, so x points in between have equal weight and maximum entropy.

We suggest that if $\exp(ibx)$ is a probability then $\exp(ib_1x)\exp(ib_2x) = \exp(i(b_1+b_2)x)$ where b is a conserved quantity. The only dynamical variable that is always conserved is p (momentum) so we suggest $\exp(ipx)$. We note that $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(-ipx) /\sqrt{L}$ removes gradations leaving maximum entropy everywhere or $P(x)dx=dx/L$.